

SHORT COMMUNICATION

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Evaluation of Prevailing Agroforestry Systems and their Components in Poonch District of Jammu and Kashmir, India

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Abstract

Agroforestry is a land use system where perennial tree species are strategically utilized in the same land management unit as animals, crops, or both, either in a temporal or spatial arrangement. Adopting various agroforestry system approaches is essential to maintaining the livelihood of farmers with limited resources, especially in rainfed areas. The aim of the study was to analyze the existing agroforestry system and its components within traditional agroforestry in the Poonch area of Jammu and Kashmir, India. Agri-silviculture, agri-horti-silviculture, silvi-pastoral and agri-silvi-pastoral were the four distinct kinds of agroforestry systems found to be prevalent in the area. It was found that the majority of the agroforestry systems in this area are made up of horticultural and multipurpose tree species in addition to crop species. In order to fully realize the potential of agroforestry as a sustainable economic and ecological solution in the area, the study calls for continued attention and support from policymakers, scientists, social workers, and extension professionals. Overall, the study highlights the need for increased promotion and development of agroforestry to improve the livelihoods of rural communities.

Keywords: Agro-forestry; Poonch; Trees; Livelihood; Agricultural crops**Introduction**

Agroforestry is the approach of growing crops, livestock, trees, and shrubs for their social, economic, and ecological benefits. The word "agroforestry" refers to a set of land-use systems where woody perennials are planted alongside livestock or herbaceous plants in a rotation, spatial arrangement, or both. Depending on the physiographic and climatic conditions, farming communities integrate various woody perennials into their agricultural system in addition to animal units to form an integrated, diverse, and productive land-use system that maximizes advantages (Pandey, 1998; Garrett et al., 2000; Nair, 1998). Agroforestry, like multifunctional agriculture, aims to promote economically, socially, and environmentally sustainable rural development while increasing agricultural productivity through nutrient recycling, soil erosion reduction, soil fertility improvement, and farm income enhancement (Leakey, 2012; Kang and Akinnifesi, 2000). Ecologically effective agroforestry systems, such as intercropping and mixed arable-livestock systems, can effectively improve the output of agriculture (Rasmussen 1988). Agroforestry is used all over the world, but it is popular in tropical and temperate regions due to its enormous socioeconomic, ecological, and cultural benefits (Nabi, 2016a; Bardhan et al., 2012; Sarmah and Arunachalam, 2011).

The impact of agroforestry on the livelihoods of rural communities differs from one community to another and is influenced by aspects such as gender, education level, and the availability of resources and infrastructure. In India, agroforestry satisfies nearly half of the fuel wood demand, two-thirds of small timber needs, 70-80% of wood required for plywood production, 60% of the raw materials for paper and pulp, and 9-11% of the green fodder necessary for livestock, in addition to meeting households' food, fruit, fiber, medicine, and timber needs (ICAR, 2010).

Most villages in Jammu and Kashmir's hilly terrain have experienced widespread migration, resulting in waste, fallow, and unproductive land, which has adversely impacted livestock-based livelihoods in rural areas. Agroforestry is crucial in enhancing local livelihoods and economies by offering a variety of products and services, and it has become a fundamental and essential component of the agricultural landscape as it promotes a mutually beneficial relationship with the farming community (Manzoor and Jazib, 2020). Tree-based fodder plays an essential role in the traditional farming system in minimising fodder scarcity concerns in J&K's hilly regions, particularly during lean seasons when fodder is scarce.

Poonch is one of the hilly districts of Jammu and Kashmir in India, and is rich in biodiversity, especially the plants. The primary livelihoods of the inhabitants revolve around agriculture and livestock rearing. Various developmental initiatives in the region have led to the overuse of natural resources, which has a direct effect on both agricultural and animal-based livelihoods. Agroforestry is viewed as a viable alternative for rural development, focusing on diverse, low-input agricultural methods that include native tree species and staple food crops. Considering the significance of agroforestry, this study was carried out to assess the current agroforestry practices in Poonch District of J&K, India.

Material and methods

Study Area

Poonch district in Jammu and Kashmir, India, is located on the southern slopes of the Pir Panjal Himalayan range, between $33^{\circ} 25'$ and $34^{\circ} 10'$ North latitude and $73^{\circ} 58'$ to $74^{\circ} 35'$ East longitude. The district has a total size of 1,674 square kilometers and is divided into six Tehsils (Haveli, Mandi, Mendhar, Surankote, Mankote, and Balakote) and eleven Blocks. The district has three different types of agro-climatic conditions for cultivating grains, vegetables, and fruit crops. The district's climate is subtropical in the south and moderate in the north, which includes hilltops. The climate in the higher regions is frigid all year round.

Fig. 1. Maps of the study area

The average minimum and maximum temperature in the district ranges from -20° to 40° Celsius. The district's average annual rainfall is approximately 1225/1388.78mm, with 56 to 73 typical rainy days; nevertheless, the higher levels of Pir Panjal receive snowfall during the winter. Agriculture, followed by pastoralism, is the sole source of income in the region. The district consists primarily of two types of soils: sub-mountainous soil in the south and meadow soil in the north. The area's different valleys also include localized wedges of alluvial material. The average landholding in the district is 0.88 hectares. With land holdings of 1-2 hectares or less, the majority of farmers in the district are marginal (71.2%) and small (18.8%) respectively.

Methodology

The present study was conducted in the Poonch district of Jammu and Kashmir UT, India. Study focused on agricultural areas primarily dominated by trees. To meet the study objectives, both primary and secondary data sources were used. The primary data was gathered mostly through field surveys and personal interviews. In the initial phase, five blocks from the area namely Poonch, Balakote, Loran, Lassana, and Mankote were selected so as to reflect the various agro-climatic conditions prevailing in the district. In the second phase ten different villages namely Ajote, Bainch, Naka Manjhari, Dharati, Madana, Shindara, Battalkote, Plera, Ghani and Balnoi were respectively chosen for the study from the selected blocks. Based on the nature of the study, field surveys were undertaken in these villages during July 2024 and March 2025.

The objective of these surveys was to gain insights into the different agroforestry practices adopted by farmers in the region. The transect walk methodology (Ram Newaj et al., 2017) was employed during the survey conducted in each selected village. During the surveys, useful information such as village names, altitudes, existing agroforestry systems, tree species, cultivated crops, and vernacular names were gathered. Secondary data were gathered from various published and unpublished sources, including the records of the J&K forest department.

Result and Discussion

Pattern of Operational Land Holdings in Poonch District

Agriculture, followed by Pastoralism, is the primary economic activity for meeting household needs. Farmers in Poonch district follow a mixed crop-livestock farming strategy. The most important cereal crops grown in the area are maize, paddy, and wheat. The majority of farmers in this area are marginal and small-scale, with average land holdings of 3.95 kanal per farmer. More than 88.6% of the district's agricultural land is rain-fed. The size of a hilly farmer's operational holdings is quite limited, and it is shrinking with population growth. The average landholding in the district is 0.88 hectares. The majority of farmers in the district are marginal (71.2%) and small (18.8%), with landholdings of 1-2 hectares or less. Based on the operational area under the farmers, the operational land holding in Poonch District is classified under five categories (table 1).

Table 1. Types of operational land holding in Poonch District

S. No.	Category of Holding	No. of Holdings	Percentage of total land	Percentage
1	Marginal Farmers	34066	32.0	71.2
2	Small Farmers	8976	30.6	18.8
3	Semi-Medium Farmers	3856	25.0	8.0
4	Medium Farmers	898	11.3	1.8
5	Large Farmers	33	1.1	0.2

Source: Agriculture Department Poonch: 2011

Agroforestry Systems in Poonch District

During the study it has been found that the following agroforestry practices are prevalent in the area. A brief description of the each identified agro-ecosystem along with the trees, agricultural crops and grasses is described below.

Agri-silviculture System

This system involves the cultivation of trees alongside agricultural crops and is quite common throughout the region. The tree species identified were *Salix alba* L. (White willow), *Celtis australis* L. (Khirk), *Albizia lebbek* (L.) Benth. (Sirin tree), *Grewia optiva* J.R.Drumm. ex Burret (Thaman), *Bauhinia variegata* L. (Kachnar), *Ziziphus mauritiana* Lam. (Beri), *Morus alba* L. (Toot), *Ficus palmata* Forssk. (Kemri), *Robinia pseudoacacia* L. (Kikar), *Juglans regia* L. (Akhroot), *Celtis australis* L. (Kirak), *Melia azedarach* L. (Dareek), *Dalbergia sissoo* DC (Tali), *Olea cuspidata* Wall ex DC. (Kohu), *Aesculus indica* Colebr. ex Camb.(Bankhori), *Populus alba* L. (Safeeda), and *Ulmus wallichiana* Planch. (Mannu) whereas the agriculture species were *Triticum aestivum* L. (Wheat), *Orzya Sativa* (Paddy), *Raphanus sativus* (Radish), *Brassica rapa* (Shalgam), *Allium sativum* L. (Garlic), *Brassica nigra* L. (Mustard), *Brassica oleracea* (Cabbage), *Pisum sativum* L. (Pea), *Solanum melogena* L. (Brinjal), *Zea mays* (Maize), *Oryza sativa* (Paddy), *Solanum tuberosum* (Potato), *Lycopersicon esculentum* (Tomato), *Capsicum frutescens* L. (Marchi), *Avena sativa* L. (Kandial), *Momordica charantia* L., (Karella), *Pennisetum glaucum* L.(Bajra), *Hibiscus esculentus* L. (Bindi), *Allium cepa* L. (Piaz), *Allium sativum* L. (lahsun), *Helianthus annulus* L. (Suraj muki), *Cucurbita pepo* L. (Dubri), *Vigna mungo* (Black gram), *Cicer arietinum* (Chickpea), *Cajanus cajan* (Pigeon peas), *Vigna radiate* (Green gram), *Phaseolus vulgaris* L. (Beans) and *Vigna unguiculata* L. Walp) (Cow peas) etc.

Agri-horti-silviculture System (Home Gardens)

This method was found to be the most prevalent agroforestry practice followed in the area. Here, people use to follow the traditional agroforestry practices like planting trees in the farm boundary and on the borders of the home compound. Three biological elements were identified in this system: trees, fruit plants, and agricultural crops. *Populus alba* L. (Safeeda), *Salix alba* L (Beesa), *Salix babylonica* L. (Kashmiri Beesa), *Ulmus villosa* Brandis ex Gamble. (Mannu), *Ulmus wallichiana* Planch. (Mannu), *Ailanthus altissima* (Mill.) Swingle (Jangli toon), *Robinia pseudoacacia* L. (Kikar), *Celtis australis* L. (Kirak), *Aesculus indica* Hook. (Bankhori), *Sapindus mukorossi* Gaertn. (Rintha), *Olea cuspidata* Wall ex DC. (Kohu), *Melia azedarach* L. (Dareek), *Grewia optiva* J.R.Drumm. ex

Burret. (Thaman), etc. were the tree species identified whereas *Malus pumila* Mill. (Seb), *Prunus armeniaca* L. (Khubani), *Prunus domestica* L. (Plum), *Prunus persica* (L.) Batsch. (Aaroo), *Phyllanthus emblica* L. (Amla) *Phoenix sylvestris* (L) Roxb. (Khajur), *Pyrus communis* L. (Nashpati), *Cydonia oblonga* Mill. (Bai), *Punica granatum* L. (Darhuni), *Pyrus pashia* Buch.Ham. ex D.Don (Batangi), *Diospyros lotus* L. (Mallok), *Eriobotrya japonica* (Loquat), *Ficus carica* L. (Kankatri Kamri), *Ficus palmata* Forssk. (Kemri/phagwara), *Juglans regia* L. (Akhroot), *Syzygium cumini* L. (Jamun), *Morus alba* L. (Toot), *Morus nigra* L. (Shahtoot) and *Citrus medica* L. (Gargal) are fruit tree species identified. The agricultural species noticed are *Raphanus sativus* (Radish), *Brassica rapa* (Turnip), *Allium sativum* L. (Garlic), *Brassica nigra* L.(Mustard), *Brassica oleracea* (Cabbage), *Pisum sativum* L. (Pea), *Solanum melogena* L. (Brinjal), *Zea mays* (Maize), *Oryza sativa* (Paddy), *Solanum tuberosum* (Potato), *Lycopersicon esculentum* (Tomato), *Capsicum frutescens* L. (Marchi), *Avena sativa* L. (Kandial), *Momordica charantia* L., (Karella), *Pennisetum glaucum* L. (Bajra), *Hibiscus esculentus* L. (Bindi), *Allium cepa* L. (Piaz), *Allium sativum* L. (lahsun), *Helianthus annulus* L. (Suraj muki) and *Cucurbita pepo* L. (Dubri) etc.

Silvi-pastoral System

This system involves the cultivation of trees along with the grasses and is mostly practiced by the pastoral community. Historically silvi-pastoral systems comprised of grazing animals in wooded rangeland and introducing trees into pastures for shade and timber. In this system *Populus alba* L. (Safeeda), *Salix alba* L (Beesa), *Salix babylonica* L. (Kashmiri Beesa), *Ulmus villosa* Brandis ex Gamble. (Mannu), *Ulmus wallichiana* Planch. (Mannu), *Ailanthus altissima* (Mill.) Swingle (Jangli toon), *Robinia pseudoacacia* L. (Kikar), *Celtis australis* L. (Kirak), *Aesculus indica* Hook. (Bankhori), *Morus alba* L. (Toot), *Morus nigra* L (Shahtoot), *Ficus palmata* Forssk. (Kemri/phagwara), *Olea cuspidata* Wall ex DC. (Kohu), *Quercus leucotrichophora* A. Camus (Rein), *Melia azedarach* L. (Dareek) and *Grewia optiva* J.R.Drumm. ex Burret. (Thaman) are tree species identified whereas grass species found were *Trifolium repens* (white clover), *Trifolium pretense* L. (red clover), *Trifolium alexandrinum*, (Shatal) *Trifolium resupinatum* L. (Shatala), *Phragmites karka* (Retz) Trim.ex. Stead. (Nari Kah), *Cynodon dactylon* (Kabal), *Capillipedium assimile* (Seta kah) *Brumus lanceolatus* (buffalo grass), *Poa persica* (Khas) *Amaranthus hybridus* (Ganhaar), *Cichorium intybus* (Kasni), *Cymbopogon spp*, *Panicum colonum*, *Saccharum spontanum* (Kal), *Sorghum halepense* (Barugass), *Imperata cylindrical*(Kulfighass), *Agrostis scabra* (Hair grass) and *Dichanthium annulatum* (Panic grass) etc.

Agroi-silvi-pastoral System

This system involves the cultivation of grass and forest trees with agricultural crops. In this system common tree species identified were *Salix alba* L (Beesa), *Salix babylonica* L. (Kashmiri Beesa), *Ulmus villosa* Brandis ex Gamble. (Mannu), *Ulmus wallichiana* Planch. (Mannu), *Ailanthus altissima* (Mill.) Swingle (Jangli toon), *Robinia pseudoacacia* L. (Kikar), *Aesculus indica* Hook. (Bankhori), *Morus alba* L. (Toot), *Morus nigra* L (Shahtoot), *Ficus palmata* Forssk. (Kemri/phagwara), *Olea cuspidata* Wall ex DC. (Kohu), *Quercus leucotrichophora* A. Camus (Rein), *Melia azedarach* L. (Dareek) and *Grewia optiva* J.R.Drumm. ex Burret. (Thaman) and *Dalbergia sissoo* DC. (Tali) etc. The agricultural species identified were *Brassica nigra* L.(Mustard), *Brassica oleracea* (Cabbage), *Pisum sativum* L. (Pea), *Solanum melogena* L. (Brinjal), *Zea mays* (Maize), *Oryza sativa* (Paddy), *Solanum tuberosum* (Potato), *Lycopersicon esculentum* (Tomato), *Capsicum frutescens* L. (Marchi), *Avena sativa* L. (Kandial), *Momordica charantia* L., (Karella), *Pennisetum glaucum* L.(Bajra), *Hibiscus esculentus* L. (Bindi) etc.

The grass species reported were *Trifolium repens* (white clover), *Trifolium pretense* (red clover), *Trifolium alexandrinum* (Shatal), *Phragmites karka* (Nari Kah), *Agrostis scabr* (Hair grass), *Brachiaria decumbens* (Signal grass), (*Paspalumnotatum* Flüggé (Bahia grass), *Dichanthium annulatum* (Marvel grass), *Chrysopogon zizanioides* (Vetiver grass), *Cymbopogon spp* (Lemon grass), *Panicum spp*, *Saccharum spontanum* (Kal), *Imperata cylindrical* (Kulfighass), *Tragopogon dubius* (Budege), *Cichorium intybus* (Handiposh), *Medicago sps* (Alfalfa), *Hordeum vulgare* (Barley) and *Sorghum halepense* (Barugass) etc.

Conclusion

Agroforestry plays an important role in rural people's livelihood security by providing fuel wood, fodder, timber, fruits, agricultural crops, vegetables, medicines, and so on, as well as significantly contributing to the household's gross annual income and employment opportunities. The study offered insightful information on this region's agroforestry environment. Four different agroforestry systems were identified, with home gardens being the most common among households. These systems demonstrate their multipurpose character by integrating a variety of tree species, livestock, and agricultural products. Study has shown that horticultural and versatile

tree species make up the majority of the agroforestry systems in this area. This study presents a list of multipurpose and horticultural tree species, including crops that can be found in farmers' agricultural fields. Documenting these multipurpose trees and agroforestry activities could be useful for introducing them to other areas within the same agro-climatic zone. The study underlines the importance of promoting and developing agroforestry to improve rural communities' livelihoods.

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